

WAYS OF INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation: This article is focused on pedagogical support for children based on development of intellectual abilities of children. Practical work of the research is being done in Uzbekistan, how to create conditions for further improving the system of preschool education, strengthening the material and technical base, expanding the network of preschool educational institutions, providing qualified pedagogical personnel, radically improving the level of preparation of children for school education, introducing modern educational programs and technologies in the educational process and moral, aesthetic and physical development of children.

Keywords: Modernization of preschool education, pedagogical support of children, intellectual development programs, preschool programs, socio-pedagogical situations, statistics, training methods.

INTRODUCTION

One of the key factors of socio-economic development in the world is the development of the intellectual potential of the individual on the basis of the requirements of the time and bringing it to a qualitatively new level. The concept of international education, developed by international organizations and most countries of the world until 2030, calls "a solid foundation of knowledge and the development of creative thinking," which, in turn, together with UNESCO, emphasizes the need to develop intellectual abilities in preschool education.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In a study aimed at enriching the theory and methodology of an individually-oriented educational process in preschool educational institutions, scientists of our republic D.A. Abdurahimova, M.K. Abdukhakimova, Criminal Code of Adamov, Z. Azizov, M. Askarov, M. Askarkhodzhaev, N.Kh. Such teachers, psychologists and philosophers as Kh. Begmatova, D.G. Boboeva, U. Butaeva, K. Okilova, F.B. Valikhodzhaeva, F.N. Vakhobova, I.V. Grosheva, L.G. Gestaeva are participating. Some aspects of child-centered education include scientists from the Commonwealth of Independent States: E.A. Avilova, A. Arushanova, M. Bakina, E. Bern, R.S. Bure, L.F. Ostrovskaya, A.G. Maslow. However, in these cases

only specific aspects of child support and child protection were considered¹.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Modern socio-pedagogical situations and the development of interdisciplinary learning processes require the determination of the theoretical foundations of pedagogical support for children. An analysis of the theory and practice of preschool education shows that the problems of intellectual development and the realization of children's opportunities at all stages of development, support and protection are reflected in the work of many scientists.

The process of preschool education, focused on a humanistic personality, is important not only because of the physical condition of the child, but also because of his or her inner world, tendencies and aspirations. In this process, the task of educators should be to find means, methods, methods and means to achieve the personal potential of children, to ensure their intellectual development, understanding of the problems of children, and not forcing them to follow their rules.

The concept of pedagogical support is based on the personality of children. The most pressing issue for this is the search for tools and forms of pedagogical support for children. Pedagogical support for children should continue uninterrupted, starting with pre-school education. Educators should not lose sight of each student's situation. They should be able to find and identify children in need. The concept of pedagogical support is a simple, friendly, operational, stimulating help aimed at solving the problems of physical, mental health, intellectual development, relationships with each other, achievements and specific problems of the educator.

In our opinion, a new look is needed on the problem of pedagogical support. At the same time, we support the idea that pedagogical support should be related to the intellectual development of the child and the individualization of his or her activity. The role of pedagogical support will thus increase the relationship between educators and children to the level of the department, provide the educator with conditions for life activities aimed at teaching and intellectual development.

The idea of comprehensive support for a growing and developing person was emphasized by many educators and psychologists. Researchers rely on didactic theories that they advocate for children.

Understanding of pedagogical support of children refers to the activities of educators with high professionalism. First of all, they can provide emergency

¹ Khayrullayeva M. Footage from the history of social and philosophical thought in Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Science, 2016. P.351.

assistance to children. Intellectual development of children is also important for solving their problems, their mental, physical health, communication, success in educational activities, their place in life and their professional orientation².

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Using the opportunities of pedagogical cooperation in the intellectual development of children through support and protection requires a number of factors³:

- The human approach to the personal development of the child in connection with the transition to a new pedagogical paradigm;
- Increasing need for new pedagogical technologies for the intellectual development and support of children;
- strengthening the essence of self-realization and organization of the child.

From this point of view, we also consider the psychological, social and philosophical foundations of a child-centered approach, support and protection. Throughout our study, we approach the development of the child's personality on the principle of cooperation. Realizing the individual strengths of the child is a priority.

CONCLUSION

In preschool educational institutions, individual and group work should be carried out aimed at the immediate and indirect solution of the child's individual problems, which should be problem-oriented and urgent.

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² Hachfeld, Axinja; Anders, Yvonne; Kuger, Susanne; и др. Triggering parental involvement for parents of different language backgrounds: the role of types of partnership activities and preschool characteristics // EARLY CHILD DEVELOPMENT AND CARE. – ENGLAND. 2016. 190-211 p.

³ Sharafutdinova X. Diagnosis and psycho-correction of mental abilities in the system of continuing education. PhD of psychology. TSPU named after Nizami, T- 2019, 53-54 p.

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